

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module A, content:

1. What is accessibility - this document
2. User needs
3. Policy and legislation
4. Accessibility standards
5. Web accessibility basics

Co-funded by
the European Union

1 What is accessibility

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Accessibility

Products and services that can be used by **all people, regardless of their abilities**

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Accessibility refers to the design and provision of products, services, environments, or information that can be easily used, understood, and accessed by individuals, regardless of their abilities or disabilities. The concept of accessibility aims to ensure that people with various physical, cognitive, sensory, and other impairments can participate fully and equally in all aspects of society.

In the context of technology and the internet, accessibility focuses on making digital content, websites, software applications, and other online resources usable by all individuals, including those with disabilities. This may involve implementing features such as screen readers, keyboard navigation, captioned videos, alternative text for images, and other adaptive technologies to accommodate users with diverse needs.

In a broader sense, accessibility also extends to physical environments, public spaces, transportation, educational facilities, and any other areas where people interact or seek services. By promoting accessibility, we strive to create an inclusive and equitable society that allows everyone to live with dignity and independence, regardless of their abilities or limitations.

Focus on user needs

- Everyone has different needs and abilities
- Provide flexibility to meet different needs

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Focusing on user needs is a fundamental principle in the design and development of any product, service, or system, including digital technologies and online resources. This approach centres around understanding and addressing the requirements, preferences, and limitations of the end-users, ensuring that the end result is not only usable but also valuable and meaningful to them.

All individuals have their specific needs, and to make sure as many as possible can use a product or service, or understand the message you are communicating, it is important to take a wide range of user needs into account. Text – or words – are often the first we think about when the topic is communication, but as many people have difficulties reading, it is important to not rely on text alone, but also provide visual support like for example illustrations, video or audio. This way of providing content in more than one format is called multimodality, and it is a key aspect of accessibility.

User groups and situations

- Persons with disabilities
- Older adults
- Not native language
- Temporary disabilities
- Situational disabilities

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Accessibility is targeting different user groups and situations:

- **Persons with disabilities:** This user group includes individuals with various physical, sensory, cognitive, or mental impairments. Designing for accessibility ensures that they can fully engage with products and services, regardless of their disabilities
- **Older adults:** This demographic comprises seniors who may experience age-related limitations or challenges in using technology. Taking their unique needs into account results in products that are more age-friendly and easy to navigate.
- **Not native language:** Users who are not native speakers of the language used in a product or service may face difficulties in understanding content. Making interfaces clear and straightforward benefits these users, promoting inclusivity and ease of use.
- **Temporary disabilities:** This category encompasses individuals with temporary impairments, such as a broken arm or temporary vision loss. Designing with their needs in mind accommodates their situational limitations during the recovery period.
- **Situational disabilities:** Users facing situational limitations, such as holding a phone while carrying groceries, may have temporary difficulties interacting with devices. Creating adaptable designs helps overcome such challenges and enhances overall usability.

Temporary barriers and disabilities

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Let's have a look at some examples of situations which involve impairments of abilities in everyday life which you may not immediately think of:

- Mobile use creates several impairments.
 - You navigate using a small screen in different situations, for example on a shaky bus, larger click areas would be good in this case.
 - Another example can be seen when you are using the mobile in different light conditions, for example on the beach or by the pool in the sun which makes it hard to read the text on a screen. In this case, good contrast is essential.
- Finally, think about what happens if your hands are busy, for example if you are carrying a child, then a door that opens automatically when it detects movement nearby is good.

Why is accessibility important in communication?

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Accessibility is crucial in communication because it ensures that information and messages reach a diverse audience, including individuals with various abilities, disabilities, and circumstances. There are several reasons why accessibility is vital in communication:

1. **Inclusivity:** Accessible communication ensures that all individuals, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, can access and understand the information being conveyed. It promotes inclusivity and prevents any form of discrimination based on a person's limitations.
2. **Equal Participation:** By making communication accessible, we enable everyone to actively participate in discussions, conversations, and the exchange of ideas. This fosters a more diverse and inclusive society where all voices are heard and valued.
3. **Compliance with Legal and Ethical Obligations:** Many countries have laws and regulations that mandate accessibility in various aspects, including communication. Organizations and institutions need to comply with these legal requirements to ensure equal opportunities for all citizens.
4. **Effective Communication:** Accessible communication enhances the effectiveness of the message delivery. When information is presented in a clear and understandable manner, it is more likely to be absorbed and retained by the intended audience.
5. **Broader Reach:** Accessibility broadens the reach of communication efforts. By accommodating diverse needs, a message can reach a larger audience, including people with disabilities and those who speak different languages or have varying

levels of literacy.

6. **Social Responsibility:** Inclusivity and accessibility are ethical responsibilities for individuals, businesses, and institutions. Emphasizing accessibility in communication reflects a commitment to social responsibility and human rights.
7. **Positive Brand Image:** Organizations that prioritize accessibility and inclusivity in their communication are viewed more favourably by the public. It enhances their brand image and reputation as socially responsible entities.
8. **Innovation and Creativity:** Embracing accessibility in communication can drive innovation and creativity. It encourages designers, content creators, and communicators to think outside the box and find innovative ways to convey messages effectively to diverse audiences.
9. **Empowerment:** Accessible communication empowers individuals with disabilities by providing them with equal access to information, education, job opportunities, and other aspects of life. It can contribute to breaking down barriers and reducing stigmas associated with disabilities.

Overall, accessibility in communication is not only a legal and moral obligation but also a strategic choice that leads to a more inclusive and equitable society. It fosters a sense of belonging and ensures that everyone can fully participate in the modern world of information and communication.

The audience is diverse

- 35% Very good reading skills
- 40% In the range between small and big difficulties
- 25% Greater difficulties, issues with concentration, memory etc.

Source: OECD

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

According to the OECD, grown up readers in most western countries can be divided into three groups.

35% of the users have very good reading skills. When communicating, you don't need to worry much about them, as they will most probably understand your message no matter how you present it.

The group you should focus on is the 25% who have difficulties reading, understanding, who experience difficulties with concentration and focus, memory etc. To make sure that this group have the best possible opportunities to read and understand your message, you need to provide accessible formats and alternatives.

The middle group of 40% who may have trouble with specific content or in a specific context, often benefit from accessibility features as well, despite not being in the core target audience for accessibility.

Disability statistics - hard to estimate!

- WHO: 15% of the world population
- EU: 87, 100 or 135 million ...?
- 30 million visually impaired
- 51 million hard of hearing
- 26 million motor impaired
- 10 million cognitive impairments

Sources: WHO, Eurostat, EBU, EFHoH

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Disability statistics are difficult. Some disabilities have medical definitions, others depend on tests or individual estimations. Personal data on abilities is very sensitive and in many countries, hard to get. One way of measuring disabilities is to look at the use of assistive technology like wheelchairs, but large user groups don't use assistive technology. The Organisations representing Persons with Disabilities may not have the financial resources to carry out scientific research.

According to the World Health Organisation, around 15% of the population - worldwide - has a disability. You can also find sources claiming 20 or even 30%. It all depends on how you measure.

According to Eurostat, 19% of young people (aged 15-24 years) reports physical or sensory limitations. This share was higher for successively older age groups, peaking at 68% among people aged 65 years and over.

The European Blind Union estimates that there are over 30 million blind and partially sighted persons in geographical Europe. This means that on average, 1 in 30 Europeans experience sight loss. There are four times as many partially sighted persons as blind persons. Women are more at risk of becoming blind or partially sighted than men.

Sight loss is closely related to old age. One in three senior citizens over 65 faces sight loss. 90 percent of visually impaired persons is over the age of 65.

The European Federation of hard of Hearing estimates that 51 million, or 9% of EU

citizens experience hearing loss, but WHO estimates it to be 15%. About one-third of older adults have hearing loss, and the chance of developing hearing loss increases with age.

The numbers for motor impairments and cognitive impairments are even harder to determine. The point is - a lot of people are affected by accessibility!

Rationale

- Engage the widest possible audience
- Accessible information is easier for everyone to understand
- In the EU: legal obligations

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Engaging the widest possible audience and making information accessible are essential goals for any communication strategy. By ensuring that information is easily understood by diverse individuals, including those with disabilities, language barriers, or varying levels of literacy, you can create a more inclusive communication – and thereby an equitable society. Accessible information benefits everyone, not just those with specific needs, as it promotes clarity, simplicity, and ease of comprehension.

By enforcing legal obligations related to accessibility, the EU seeks to create a more inclusive digital environment, where all citizens can access information, services, and participate fully in society without any discrimination based on disabilities or other limitations. These legal measures also encourage businesses, organizations, and service providers to adopt accessibility best practices voluntarily, extending the benefits of accessible information to a broader audience beyond just the public sector.

Reflection / discussion

- Have you experienced having a disability?
- Do you know someone who has a disability?
- Were you surprised by the statistics, or was it the number you expected?

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Let the students reflect on how we determine what a disability really is.

Resources

- European Disability Forum, EDF
<https://www.edf-feph.org>
- World Health Organisation WHO
<https://www.who.int>
- Eurostat
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module A, content:

1. What is accessibility
2. User needs - this document
3. Policy and legislation
4. Accessibility standards
5. Web accessibility basics

Co-funded by
the European Union

2 User needs

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curriculum

Co-funded by
the European Union

Groups of user needs

- Usage **without** vision
- Usage with **limited** vision
- Usage **without** perception of colour
- Usage **without** hearing
- Usage with **limited** hearing
- Usage with **limited** vocal capability
- Usage **without** manipulation or strength
- Usage **without** photosensitive seizure triggers
- Usage with **limited** cognition

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

There are many ways of grouping user needs when it comes to accessibility. In this training, we are using the so called functional performance statements of the European standard that contain the minimum requirements of the Web Accessibility Directive (the standard is called EN301549). We will present each user group separately.

Usage without vision

Users access written information (documents, websites, books) through assistive technology that transform written information to audio or braille

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Blind users rely on assistive technology to access written information in various formats. Two common forms of assistive technology used for this purpose are screen readers and braille displays.

Screen Readers: Screen readers are software applications that convert on-screen text into synthesized speech or braille output. They can read aloud the content of documents, websites, and other digital materials, enabling users with visual impairments to access information independently. Screen readers interpret the content based on the underlying structure and markup of the document, such as HTML tags on websites or proper heading structures in documents.

Braille Displays are hardware peripherals that allow users to read digital text in braille. These devices have a series of small pins that dynamically raise and lower to form braille characters based on the digital content being displayed. Users can read the braille output using their fingertips, providing a tactile representation of the written information.

An alternative to the braille display is audio.

For blind users, these assistive technologies play a critical role in making written information accessible. By transforming text into audio or braille, blind users can access a wide range of materials, including documents, websites, books, educational resources, and more independently. This ensures equal participation in education, work, and various aspects of daily life, promoting inclusivity and independence.

Accessibility - without vision

- Structuring text properly, using headings, preambles, sections etc correctly, so the assistive technology can interpret the information and provide it to the user in an organised way
- Providing text alternatives for non-text information (such as images)

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/info-and-relationships>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/non-text-content>

Usage with limited vision

- Users with limited vision benefit from magnification
- Users with limited vision benefit from good contrast between text and background

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Users with limited vision can benefit from various accessibility features that enhance readability and visual clarity. Two essential aspects that significantly improve their experience are magnification and good contrast between text and background:

Magnification: Many individuals with limited vision use screen magnification tools or built-in accessibility features on devices to enlarge text and graphical elements. By allowing users to increase the size of the content, they can read text more comfortably and discern graphical details with greater ease. Providing content that remains legible and usable at higher magnification levels ensures a positive user experience for people with limited vision.

Contrast: Good contrast between text and background is critical for users with limited vision, as it enhances the visibility of the content. A high contrast ratio makes text stand out from the background, making it easier to read. Consider using dark text on a light background or vice versa to ensure maximum contrast. Avoid low contrast combinations that may strain the eyes or make it difficult for users with limited vision to distinguish the text.

Implementing these features not only benefits users with limited vision but also improves the overall accessibility of your content for a broader audience. Ensuring that

your website, documents, and digital materials offer options for increased magnification and have excellent contrast makes the information more accessible and usable to people with varying visual abilities. This commitment to accessibility aligns with the principles of inclusive design, creating a more inclusive and welcoming experience for all users.

Accessibility - limited vision

- Making sure that the graphical design allows for magnification
- Make sure to provide enough contrast between text and background

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/resize-text>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/contrast-minimum>

Usage without perception of colour

- Users who are colour-blind cannot distinguish between different colours.
- This may also affect the way information is perceived on a screen.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Colour blindness is a common visual impairment that affects how individuals perceive and distinguish colours. People with colour vision deficiencies may have difficulty differentiating certain colours or may not perceive colours at all. This condition can impact the way information is conveyed and understood, especially in digital environments where colour is often used for various purposes, such as conveying meaning, highlighting elements, or organizing content.

Accessibility

- no perception of colour

- Do not rely on colour alone to convey meaning in communication. For example:
 - Make sure links are visually marked with colour plus something more, like underline, bold or an icon.
 - In diagrams or pie charts, combine colour with patterns.

Notes

Use Colour with Caution: Avoid using colour alone to convey important information. For example, do not use colour as the only means to differentiate between different options or indicate errors. Instead, use colour in combination with other visual cues, such as text labels, icons, or patterns.

Usage without hearing

Users who are born deaf have sign language as their first language.

Although most understand written language, it can be likened to a foreign language.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Deaf individuals who are born deaf or acquire deafness early in life often have sign language as their first language. Sign language is a visual-gestural language with its own grammar, syntax, and cultural nuances, distinct from spoken languages. For these individuals, sign language is the primary means of communication, and it is how they naturally interact and express themselves.

Written language, on the other hand, can be considered a second language for many deaf individuals. While some deaf individuals may understand written language well, others may find it challenging, similar to learning a foreign language. This is because sign language and written language have different linguistic structures and modalities.

Accessibility - no hearing

- The key to ensure accessibility for this user group is to provide information in the local sign language.
- Captions can also be useful for this user group, but not all deaf users read well.

Notes

Sign languages are not modelled on spoken languages. They are languages in their own right, with equally complex rules, grammatical structures and vocabulary that evolve and vary by region, social and age groups; convey meanings and emotions; create social and family bonds; and meet artistic and identity needs. The EU has a large variety of sign languages, including a French sign language in France, (a different) French and Flemish sign languages in Belgium, as well as, for example, Catalan and Galician sign languages as well as the Spanish sign language in Spain.

There is not (yet) any automatic sign language services, so sign language has to be provided by live interpreters.

For some deaf users, captions can be of help too.

Usage with limited hearing

Users who are hard of hearing can have difficulties perceiving video or audio on the web.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

People who experience limiting hearing abilities range from mild or moderate hearing loss in one or both ears (“hard of hearing”).

Some people with auditory disabilities can hear sounds but often not sufficiently to understand all speech, especially when there is background noise. This can include people using hearing aids, but estimations show that only around half of the users (in developed countries) who would benefit from hearing aids actually have - or use - them.

To be hard of hearing often means challenges in the social life.

Accessibility - limited hearing

- Provide captions for videos
- Provide text alternatives (such as transcripts) for audio

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/captions-prerecorded>

Usage without manipulation or strength

Users with motor impairments may use different assistive technology devices for input; voice control, sip-and-puff mouse, eye tracking or special keyboard and/or mouse.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Motor impairments include weakness and limitations of muscular control (like involuntary movements including tremors, lack of coordination, or paralysis), limitations of sensation, joint disorders (such as arthritis), pain that impedes movement, and missing limbs.

This user group rely on keyboard support to activate functionality provided on web pages, while using different kind of input devices. They may need more time to type, click, or carry out other interaction, and even type one character at a time.

Accessibility - motor impairment

- Ensure clickable areas are big enough to hit
- Do not place objects too close to each other

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

People with motor impairments may have trouble clicking small areas and are more likely to make mistakes in typing and clicking. Providing large clickable areas, enough time to complete tasks, and error correction options for forms are important design aspects. Other important design aspects include providing visible indicators of the current focus, and mechanisms to skip over blocks, such as over page headers or navigation bars.

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/keyboard>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/focus-visible>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/target-size>

Usage with limited cognition

Difficulties with understanding content, keeping attention and focus or completing tasks that are complex or involve using their memory.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Cognitive impairment is when a person has trouble remembering, learning new things, concentrating, or making decisions that affect their everyday life. Cognitive impairment ranges from mild to severe. With mild impairment, people may begin

to notice changes in cognitive functions, but still be able to do their everyday activities. Severe levels of impairment can lead to losing the ability to understand the meaning or importance of something and the ability to talk or write, resulting in the inability to live independently.

Accessibility - cognition

- Writing in plain language or easy-to-read
- Complementing text with illustrations to enhance understanding
- Using bullet points or other visual elements to break up texts and guide the reader
- Provide explanations for difficult words and concepts

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/reading-level>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/WCAG21/Understanding/consistent-navigation>

Exercise / activity

The best activity to understand user needs is to meet people with disabilities. Invite some into the classroom and discuss!

Co-funded by
the European Union

Look at videos with end users

Look at videos with people with disabilities using assistive technology, for example:

- [Dyslexia](#)
- [Motor impairments](#)
- [Visual impairments](#)
- [Blind](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

If meeting end users is not an option, watching a video where end users use assistive technology can be a way to understand the topic.

Simulations

Try some of the simulation features you can find online, for example:

- [Colour blindness simulator](#)
- [Disability simulator](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

NB using simulation features can of course never replace working close to real users. But if you use it as a “teaser” or a way to get some very basic insights or thought around what accessibility is about, it can be a good first step – allowing you to be more curious.

Resources

- [International Association of Accessibility Professionals: CPACC Body of Knowledge](#)
- [ITU: Self Paced Online Training on ICT Accessibility](#)
- [UK GOV: Resources on accessibility](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module A, content:

1. What is accessibility
2. User needs - this document
3. Policy and legislation - this document
4. Accessibility standards
5. Web accessibility basics

Co-funded by
the European Union

3 Policy and legislation

Co-funded by
the European Union

Digital accessibility in the EU

- UNCRPD
- Disability Strategy
- Marrakesh Treaty
- Procurement Directive
- Web Accessibility Directive
- European Accessibility Act

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

In the EU, accessibility policies are based on the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, UNCRPD, which is ratified not only by the member states but also as the EU as such. THE European Commission is developing multi-year strategies to implement activities that supports the UNCRPD. The recent policy document is called the [Strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities 2021-2030](#).

The aim of the strategy is to ensure that all persons with disabilities in Europe:

- enjoy their human rights
- have equal opportunities, equal access to participate in society and economy
- are able to decide where, how and with whom they live
- move freely in the EU regardless of their support needs
- and no longer experience discrimination

As part of the strategy, the commission presents legal initiatives, research funding and flagship initiatives like the [Disability card](#).

In recent years, several legal acts on digital accessibility have been implemented:

The primary goal of the Marrakesh Treaty is to enhance access to published works for people with print disabilities, such as individuals who are blind, visually impaired, or have other difficulties accessing printed materials. It aims to address the "book famine" experienced by print-disabled individuals worldwide by enabling greater access to books and other literary works in accessible formats.

The Procurement Directive was updated in 2017 to cover accessibility requirements in public procurement.

The Web Accessibility Directive entered into force in 2018 and requires public sector websites and apps to be accessible by meeting minimum criteria defined in a European standard (EN301549).

The European Accessibility Act will enter into force in 2025 and requires certain products and services to be accessible by meeting minimum criteria defined in European standards.

Procurement Directive

- Public procurement of goods and services
- Increased requirements 2017
- Competitors can complain
- Further support in 2025
- Technical requirements (EN301549)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The updated text on accessibility in the Directive is under Article 42, Technical specifications :

“For all procurement which is intended for use by natural persons, whether general public or staff of the contracting authority, the technical specifications shall, except in duly justified cases, be drawn up so as to take into account accessibility criteria for persons with disabilities or design for all users.

Where mandatory accessibility requirements are adopted by a legal act of the Union, technical specifications shall, as far as accessibility criteria for persons with disabilities or design for all users are concerned, be defined by reference thereto.”

Currently, the only way to enforce this requirements is for competing bidders to file a complaint. This means that the law gives a strong incentive to procure accessible goods and services and supports organisations who want to point to an official document to underline importance. But it is still easy to dodge the requirements if a public procurer prefers to focus on other requirements.

With the European Accessibility Act, the actual requirements are indirectly specified to align with other accessibility legislation in the region and beyond (i.e. EN301549)

Web Accessibility Directive

- In force since 23 September 2018
- Harmonised minimum requirements
- Technical specifications (EN301549)
- Public sector and bodies governed by public law
- National monitoring

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The Web Accessibility Directive entered into force in 2018. It is a minimum harmonisation directive, which means that member states may go beyond the requirements, but cannot do less. The European standard EN30159 Annex A contains the minimum requirements (so called presumed conformance).

The directive covers the public sector and “bodies governed by public law” This means: (1) any body established for the specific purpose of meeting needs in the general interest, not having an industrial or commercial character, (2) having legal personality and (3) financed, for the most part, by the State, regional or local authorities, or other bodies governed by public law; or subject to management supervision by those bodies; or having an administrative, managerial or supervisory board, more than half of whose members are appointed by the State, regional or local authorities, or by other bodies governed by public law;

The directive is enforced by national monitoring bodies who carry out regular supervision of the websites and apps in scope of the directive.

Scope

- Websites
- Intranets
- Extranets
- Documents
- Apps

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The scope of the directive is websites, intranets, extranets, documents and apps of public sector (and bodies governed by public law)

Not in scope

- Live-video
- Maps (alternative required for navigation)
- Cultural heritage reproductions
- Third-party content
- Documents published **before** 23 September 2018
- Archived material not needed for administrative processes nor updated **after** 23 September 2019

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The directive does not apply to

This Directive does not apply to the following content of websites and mobile applications:

- office file formats published before 23 September 2018, unless such content is needed for active administrative processes relating to the tasks performed by the public sector body concerned;
- pre-recorded time-based media published before 23 September 2020;
- live time-based media;
- online maps and mapping services, as long as essential information is provided in an accessible digital manner for maps intended for navigational use;
- third-party content that is neither funded nor developed by, nor under the control of, the public sector body concerned;
- reproductions of items in heritage collections that cannot be made fully accessible because of either:

- the incompatibility of accessibility requirements with either the preservation of the item concerned or the authenticity of the reproduction (e.g. contrast); or
- the unavailability of automated and cost-efficient solutions that would easily extract the text of manuscripts or other items in heritage collections and transform it into content compatible with the accessibility requirements;
- content of extranets and intranets, that is to say, websites that are only available for a closed group of people and not to the general public as such, published before 23 September 2019, until such websites undergo a substantial revision;
- content of websites and mobile applications qualifying as archives, meaning that they only contain content that is neither needed for active administrative processes nor updated or edited after 23 September 2019.

Three parts of enforcement

- National monitoring body
- Accessibility statement
- Feedback from users

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The monitoring is top down, controlling that the objects in scope are accessible and reporting to the European Commission.

The public sector bodies and others in scope of the directive have to self-declare their level of accessibility and publish an accessibility statement.

End users have the right to provide feedback on digital services or content they can't access, and, if not accessible, may require alternative formats.

Accessibility statement

- Compulsory on all public websites
- Detailed and clear
- What is not accessible and why
- Mechanism for users to provide feedback

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The accessibility statement has two target audiences: the monitoring agency and the end users.

The statement should contain both an overview of possible issues and a mechanism for end users to provide feedback.

European Accessibility Act

- In force from 28 June 2025
- Harmonised minimum requirements
- Technical specifications (EN301549)
- Manufacturers, representatives, importers and distributors
- Certain products and services
- National monitoring

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The upcoming European Accessibility Act will enter into force in 2024.

It has already some requirements in the law itself, but will be accompanied by new and updated standards for the technical specifications.

The act covers all parts of the value-chain: manufacturers, representatives, importers and distributors of certain products and services.

Just like the WAD, it will be monitored at national level.

Scope: products

- Computers, operating systems and smart phones
- Payment terminals, self-service terminals
- Electronic terminals for communication
- Digital TV
- E-readers

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The products in scope of the act are:

- consumer general purpose computer hardware systems and operating systems for those hardware systems;
- the following self-service terminals:
 - payment terminals;
 - the following self-service terminals dedicated to the provision of services covered by this Directive
 - automated teller machines;
 - ticketing machines;
 - check-in machines;
 - interactive self-service terminals providing information, excluding terminals installed as integrated parts of vehicles, aircrafts, ships or rolling stock;
- consumer terminal equipment with interactive computing capability, used for electronic communications services;

- consumer terminal equipment with interactive computing capability, used for accessing audiovisual media services; and
- e-readers

Scope: services

- Electronic communications services
- Streaming services
- Transportation: NB only digital services
- E-books and software
- E-commerce
- Consumer banking services

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The services in scope of the act are:

- electronic communications services with the exception of transmission services used for the provision of machine-to-machine services;
- services providing access to audiovisual media services;
- the following elements of air, bus, rail and waterborne passenger transport services, except for urban, suburban and regional transport services for which only the elements under point (v.) apply:
 - i. websites;
 - ii. mobile device-based services including mobile applications;
 - iii. electronic tickets and electronic ticketing services;
 - iv. delivery of transport service information, including real-time travel information; this shall, with regard to information screens, be limited to interactive screens located within the territory of the Union; and

- v. interactive self-service terminals located within the territory of the Union, except those installed as integrated parts of vehicles, aircrafts, ships and rolling stock used in the provision of any part of such passenger transport services;
- consumer banking services;
- e-books and dedicated software; and
- e-commerce services.

Not in scope

- Pre-recorded video published before 28 June 2025
- Documents published before 28 June 2025
- Maps (alternative required for navigation)
- Third-party content
- Archived material not needed for administrative processes nor updated **after** 28 June 2025

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The act does not apply to:

- pre-recorded time-based media published before 28 June 2025;
- office file formats published before 28 June 2025;
- online maps and mapping services, if essential information is provided in an accessible digital manner for maps intended for navigational use;
- third-party content that is neither funded, developed by, or under the control of, the economic operator concerned;
- content of websites and mobile applications qualifying as archives, meaning that they only contain content that is not updated or edited after 28 June 2025.

Micro enterprises - not in scope of services

- < 10 employees
- < €10 million turn over OR balance sheet > €2 million

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Micro enterprises offering products are in scope of the act, but micro enterprises offering services are not in scope.

The definition of a micro enterprise is a company with fewer than 10 employees and an annual turnover (the amount of money taken in a particular period) or balance sheet (a statement of a company's assets and liabilities) below €2 million.

Exercise / activity

- Look for an Accessibility Statement on a public sector website or app. Do you understand it? Feel free to provide constructive feedback!
- List the 10 most important digital services you use. Are they covered by any of the directives?

Resources

- [UNCRPD](#)
- [EU Disability Strategy 2021-2030](#)
- [Marrakesh Treaty](#)
- [Procurement Directive](#)
- [Web Accessibility Directive](#)
- [European Accessibility Act](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

National legislation

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Relevant laws

- Transposed EU-directives
- Anti-discrimination laws
- Laws on education
- Laws on employment
- Language laws

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

The EU member states also have national laws that are relevant to take into account. These are just examples of types/areas of legislation where you may find interesting national rules.

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module A, content:

1. What is accessibility
2. User needs - this document
3. Policy and legislation
4. **Accessibility standards - this document**
5. Web accessibility basics

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

4 Accessibility standards

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

EN 301 549

Accessibility Requirements for ICT Products and Services

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

European norm EN 301 549

- CEN/CENELEC/ETSI
- Harmonised standard
 - presumed conformance
- Current version 3.2.1
- Updated in 2025

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

When European legislation points to standards for technical specifications, these standards need to be harmonised European standards, so called European norms (EN). For web accessibility, the most important standard is the EN301549. This standards cover ICT products and services and was originally developed to support the 2017 update of the procurement directive. Annex A contains the minimum requirements of the Web Accessibility Directive, and the standard is currently being updated to support the European Accessibility Directive in the same way.

Content of the standard

0-3: Background, Definitions etc
4: Functional performance
5: Generic requirements
6: ICT and two-way voice communication
7: ICT with video possibilities
8: Hardware

9: Web
10: Non-web documents
11: Software
12: Documentation and support services
13: ICT for emergency services
14: Conformance

Co-funded by
the European Union

Useful Annexes

Annex A: Relationship with the Web Accessibility Directive

Annex B: Relationship between requirements and functional performance statements

Annex C: Determination of conformance

Annex D: Further resources for cognitive accessibility

Annex E: Guidance for usage of the standard

Co-funded by
the European Union

Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

WCAG 2.1

- W3C
- Global standard
- Current version 2.1 (new version 2023/4)
- Three levels:
 - A
 - AA
 - AAA

Notes

Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) is a global standard developed by W3C.

To avoid having 2 standards covering the same things, the EN301549 is referencing WCAG when it comes to web accessibility. This means that the EU and for example the US can have the same minimum requirements. However, the US legislation is still pointing to the old version of WCAG (2.0), whereas the EN301549 references WCAG 2.1.

The next version, WCAG 2.2, will most probably be released as a stable standard during the last part of 2023 or early 2024.

There are three levels of conformance to WCAG:

- Level A is the minimum level.
- Level AA includes all Level A and AA requirements. This is the level EN301549 references.
- Level AAA includes all Level A, AA, and AAA requirements. According to W3C, all level AAA success criteria is not possible to satisfy for some content.

Perceivable

Operable

Understandable

Robust

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

WCAG is divided into 4 Principles of Accessibility (explained in the following pages).

Perceivable

Users must be able to perceive the information being presented (it can't be invisible to all of their senses)

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Operable

Users must be able to operate the interface (the interface cannot require interaction that a user cannot perform)

Understandable

Users must be able to understand the information as well as the operation of the user interface (the content or operation cannot be beyond their understanding)...

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Robust

Users must be able to access the content as technologies advance (as technologies and user agents evolve, the content should remain accessible)

Communications-related criteria

- a) Technical skills: how to make sure the content can be used by people with assistive technology
- b) Structure and layout skills: how to make the order of content logical and place objects in an understandable way
- c) Content skills: how to write readable text, explain difficult words and provide visual elements to enhance understanding

Co-funded by
the European Union

Perceivable to all audiences

- Making documents and websites accessible and compatible with assistive technology
- Providing options to non-text-based information, including images but also audio
- And more...

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Understandable to all audiences

- Structuring texts in readable chunks
- Plain language as a standard way of writing
- Using combinations of text and images to enhance information
- And more...

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise / activity

- Plenty of free resources available
 - [Colour contrast analyser](#)
 - [PDF accessibility checker](#)
 - [Website accessibility checker](#)
- NB: Manual checks are needed for full audit

Resources

- [EN 301 549](#)
- [The EN videos](#)
- [WCAG 2.1](#)
- [W3Cs list of tools for automatic testing](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module A, content:

1. What is accessibility
2. User needs - this document
3. Policy and legislation
4. Accessibility standards
5. Web accessibility basics - this document

Co-funded by
the European Union

5 Web accessibility basics

Co-funded by
the European Union

Important for everyone

- Find information
- Navigate from one part of the website to another
- Understand the context
- Trust the information provided

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Basic recommendations on accessible communication is often just common sense. What is good for all users are necessary for some.

Making it easy to find information, to navigate between different parts of content, to understand the information you find and to trust the information when found, that all sounds very obvious. But when it becomes hard to find what you are looking for, if navigation is cumbersome and the content difficult to understand and trust - then any user would be frustrated. Therefore, it is important that as many users as possible can find, navigate, understand and trust your content.

Key elements of accessibility

- Structure
- Providing alternatives
- Technical requirements
- Consistency in design

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Accessibility consists of several key elements, where two are explicitly important for communication: structure and alternatives.

Structure

- Headings
- Text body in sections
- Bullet points
- Consistent placement of elements (buttons etc)

Important for all, necessary for users with visual or motor impairments

Notes

Make sure your website or document use real headings (use styles for formatting in Word, for example).

Divide the text into sections to facilitate reading.

Use bullet points for lists etc

Make sure to be consistent when placing recurring objects, so users recognise the layout - that is important to build trust.

These are examples that are important to all users, but necessary for some.

Provide alternatives

- Alternative texts for images
- Illustrations to text
- Captions for video
- Transcript for audio

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

People have needs and preferences, so providing alternatives is a good start if you want to make something accessible. When you publish an image, make sure to add an alternative text so that people who are blind get the same information. When you have a lot of text, add illustrations to it to make it easier to follow for people who are dyslectic or have a cognitive impairment. When you publish a video, make sure it has captions so that people who are hard of hearing get the same information. When you publish a podcast or some other kind of audio, make sure to add a transcript so that people who are hard of hearing get the same information

Exercise / activity

- Go to Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn and look for images marked with "ALT" for Alternative text. Out of the first 10 images you found, how many had an alternative text?
- Go to YouTube and find 3 short videos you are interested in. How many of these are captioned?

Resources

- [How to write ALT-texts](#)
- [How to caption a video](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap) – this document
7. What is accessible communication
8. Requirements in practice
9. Inclusive communication
10. Communication strategy
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events

Co-funded by
the European Union

6 Accessible communication

Co-funded by
the European Union

Why communicate accessibly?

- Engage the widest possible audience
- Accessible information is easier for everyone to understand
- In the EU: legal obligations

Co-funded by
the European Union

Accessibility

Products and services that can be used by **all people, regardless of their abilities**

Co-funded by
the European Union

User needs in centre

- Everyone has different needs and abilities
- Provide flexibility to meet different needs

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Inclusive mindset

- Recognise diversity of the audience and their needs
- Strive to give equivalent information to everyone

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication - this document
8. Requirements in practice
9. Inclusive communication
10. Communication strategy
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events

Co-funded by
the European Union

7 What is accessible communication

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Communication that everyone
can **perceive** and **understand**
regardless of ability

Perceivable communication

- Information that is **not dependent** on the audience having a specific ability
- Provide an alternative

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

Accessibility is about providing choice. People prefer or need to perceive information in different ways. That is why alternatives are important.

The first principle: Perceivable

- Text alternative
- Time-based media
- Adaptable
- Distinguishable

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

From the principle of perceivable information, we are going to look closer at four parts; text alternatives, time-based media, adaptable information and distinguishable information.

Text alternative

- Provide alternative text for images
 - Websites
 - Apps
 - Social media
 - Documents

Notes

When you publish an image that convey meaning (and is not just decorative), you need to provide an alternative text to describe it. This is necessary to make sure blind people get equivalent information as others.

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#non-text-content>

Example: Good ALT-texts

DO

- Descriptive, non-judgmental and conveys the message of the image.
- Concise, no more than 150 characters.
- Written as a sentence with a full stop at the end.
- Example:
 - A display of fruits in a grocery store.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Example: ALT-text on a webpage

- We can use the element to put images on a webpage.
- The element requires an alt-attribute, and its value is the textual description of the image (ALT-text).

The main objective of the ADORE project is to educate university teaching and training staff working in the field of communication on accessible content publishing and how to provide a more inclusive teaching experience for all students.

alt="Students using computers. Photo."

Example: ALT-text in an app

- There are different ways to determine if ALT-texts are present in apps.
- Navigate the app with a screen reader like VoiceOver (iOS), TalkBack (Android) or Narrator (Windows). The screen reader will announce if ALT-texts are present for the images.

Example: ALT-text in social media

- It is possible to add alternative text for images on social media.
- For example, Twitter has an image description reminder to help you remember.
- To activate it: Settings and privacy > Accessibility, display, and languages > Accessibility > Receive image description reminder.

Example: ALT-text in a document

- It is simple to add ALT-texts to your images in documents, or to mark images as decorative.
- The automatic generated ALT-texts are getting better, but always check them manually.

Time-based media

- Time-based media
 - Captions for video
 - Audio description for video
 - Transcript for audio

Notes

When you publish a video or audio, you need to provide captions or transcripts. This is necessary to make sure hard of hearing people get equivalent information as others.

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#captions-prerecorded>

Adaptable

- Info and relationships
- Meaningful sequence
- Orientation
- Identify input purpose

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

When it comes to making interfaces adaptable, there are several aspects to bear in mind.

Example: Info and relationships

DO

- The different parts of the text - such as headings, paragraphs, and lists - have the correct formatting.
- The heading structure begins with a main heading.
- The heading structure is logical and represents the hierarchy of the content.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#info-and-relationships>

Example: Meaningful sequence

DO

A document consists of multiple columns. The content's reading order is logical and reflect the visual order. Therefore, assistive technology will present the content in a correct order.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#meaningful-sequence>

Example: Orientation

DO ✓

Based on the user's chosen orientation when watching a video, it is shown in either portrait or landscape mode.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#orientation>

Example: Identify input purpose DO

The user can let the browser save frequently occurring information, such as name and email address. The form fields for name and email fill automatically.

First name
John

Last name
Doe

Email
john.doe@email.com

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#identify-input-purpose>

Distinguishable

- Use of colour
- Minimum contrast
- Resize text
- Images of text
- Reflow
- Text spacing

Notes

When it comes to making the interface distinguishable, not all parts are always possible to change for the author. But you can always ask the designer to help you.

Example: Use of colour

DON'T

Do not use colour alone to indicate links.

Digital Dialogue: The Online Exchange

The internet has transformed how we communicate. Dive into the world of [online forums](#) where discussions span topics from science to pop culture. Engage in meaningful conversations that transcend geographical boundaries.

Nonverbal Communication: Beyond Words

Sometimes, the unspoken says the most. Delve into the art of [nonverbal communication](#) and learn how gestures, facial expressions, and body language convey emotions and intentions.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#use-of-color>

Example: Use of colour

DON'T

When viewing the links in black and white, it becomes almost impossible to differentiate the links from regular text.

Digital Dialogue: The Online Exchange

The internet has transformed how we communicate. Dive into the world of [online forums](#) where discussions span topics from science to pop culture. Engage in meaningful conversations that transcend geographical boundaries.

Nonverbal Communication: Beyond Words

Sometimes, the unspoken says the most. Delve into the art of [nonverbal communication](#) and learn how gestures, facial expressions, and body language convey emotions and intentions.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#use-of-color>

Example: Use of colour

DO

- Use at least one more way to convey information, in addition to colour.
- Links can be underlined or supplemented with an icon, for example.

Digital Dialogue: The Online Exchange

The internet has transformed how we communicate. Dive into the world of [online forums](#) where discussions span topics from science to pop culture. Engage in meaningful conversations that transcend geographical boundaries.

Nonverbal Communication: Beyond Words

Sometimes, the unspoken says the most. Delve into the art of [nonverbal communication](#) and learn how gestures, facial expressions, and body language convey emotions and intentions.

Example: Minimum contrast

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#contrast-minimum>

Example: Resize text

DON'T

The user is not able to resize the text without assistive technology up to 200 percent. There is loss of content or functionality.

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#resize-text>

Example: Resize text

DO

The user is able to resize the text without assistive technology up to 200 percent. There is no loss of content or functionality.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#resize-text>

Example: Images of text

DON'T

Textual information is provided through an image of text.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#images-of-text>

Example: Images of text

DO

Textual information is provided in actual text.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#images-of-text>

Example: Reflow

DO ✓

The user can use the interface, regardless of their screen size. The content is presented without loss of information and functionality. The user does not have to scroll sideways.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#reflow>

Example: Text spacing

DO

The user can adjust the spacing between letters, words, lines and paragraphs.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#text-spacing>

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication
- 8. Requirements in practice - this document**
9. Inclusive communication
10. Communication strategy
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

8 Requirements in practice

Co-funded by
the European Union

Always test with users

- Create web content and documents that can be read by screen readers
- Test content with screen readers to verify accessibility for blind users

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Understandable communication

Information that is easy to understand by everyone, including persons who for various reasons have difficulties reading or processing information.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Simplify and explain

- Plain language
- Avoid jargon or specialised language
- Provide background knowledge
- Highlight main ideas to guide the audience

Options for understanding

- Combine text and images to enhance message
- Provide audio/video options
- Plain language
- Easy to read summaries

Resources

- [Plain language](#)
- [Easy to read](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Exercise

- Select (part of) a formal text from a bank, an e-commerce site or a government website. See if you can re-write it to become more understandable for everyone? Try to use tips from Plain Language and/or Easy to Read.

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication
8. Requirements in practice
- 9. Inclusive communication - this document**
10. Communication strategy
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

9 Inclusive communication

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Inclusive portrayals

- Representation in contexts that does not focus on disability
- Nothing about us without us
- Acknowledge individual differences
- People first language

Co-funded by
the European Union

Inclusive language

People first:

Put the individual at the centre, not the disability

(e.g. a person with a visual impairment)

Some activists prefer identity first

(e.g. "the Deaf community")

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication
8. Requirements in practice
9. Inclusive communication
- 10. Communication strategy - this document**
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events

10 Communication strategy

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Planning

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Elements of strategy

- Set reasonable goals and follow up
- Identify required formats and develop the strategy to meet the needs
- Assign responsibility to ensure consistency across platforms and formats
- Draft accessibility statement and develop plan to implement strategy

Co-funded by
the European Union

Goals

- The world's most accessible communication
- Communication that reaches as many as possible with limited means
- Compliant communication
- Specific target audience only

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Formats

Text

Images

Audio

Video

Each format has their own accessibility requirements

Responsibilities

Assign accessibility responsibilities among team members according to job role and/or skills.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Formalise the plan

- Set the ambition - draft an accessibility statement
- Detail concrete objectives
- Set deadlines
- Set up evaluation procedures

Form good habits

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Purposeful approach

- Involve colleagues
- Document progress
- Evaluate and ask for feedback
- Ambition matters: do it step by step

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Work with colleagues

- Discuss the accessibility of a content item with a colleague or mentor
- Establish an accessibility task force and reflect on practice together
- Train yourself and colleagues

Document progress

- Use checklists
- Keep a journal: take notes on your approach for reflection later on
- Progressively integrate accessible practices in organisational routine

Where to start?

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

1

Example: Little time

- Use built-in features in Word, Acrobat, Ppt to check accessibility
- Use an automatic tool to check website accessibility
- See a free lecture on accessibility, read up on particular topics

2

Example: Medium time

- Develop and try out options for multimodality (adding images, video, audio to enhance content).
- Practice and improve on plain language and easy to read techniques
- Do a simulation exercise to experience how your content works for different audiences

3

Example: More time

- Learn more about the standards behind accessibility (EN 301549)
- Join accessibility communities to share experiences (for example International Association of Accessibility Professionals)
- Set up regular meetings with persons with disabilities to receive feedback on your content

Exercise / activity

- Think of at least two different communication tasks (for example: We are developing a specific marketing campaign during the summer vs We are developing our new website). Which of the three scenarios described fit into each of these? What are the key points to consider (budget, time, competence, target audience etc)?

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](#)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication
8. Requirements in practice
9. Inclusive communication
10. Communication strategy
- 11. Accessible content - this document**
12. Accessible events

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

11 Accessible content

Co-funded by
the European Union

Text : technical aspects

Co-funded by
the European Union

Ensure perception

- No images of text
- Check with assistive technology
- Zoomable 200%
- Contrasts

Co-funded by
the European Union

Content should be possible to magnify

Object Object

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#resize-text>

Pay attention to contrasts

Bad text contrasts make reading difficult

Good text contrasts make reading easier

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#contrast-minimum>

Readability

- Structure and formatting (headings, sections)
- Use standard fonts
- Alignment: not justified

Co-funded by
the European Union

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#headings-and-labels>

DON'T

The diagram shows a vertical rectangular box representing a document layout. It contains three sections, each starting with a heading in a rounded rectangle: "Heading 1", "Heading 2", and "Heading 3".

- Heading 1:** Followed by three horizontal lines representing text.
- Heading 2:** Followed by three horizontal lines representing text.
- Heading 3:** Followed by three bullet points, each with a horizontal line representing text.

To the right of the box, the text "DO" is displayed next to a green checkmark, indicating that this structure is a recommended practice.

At the bottom right of the slide, there are two logos: the "adore" logo (Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula) and the European Union flag with the text "Co-funded by the European Union".

Notes

... and use bullet lists to highlight information.

Formatting helps users to prioritise. Formatting helps users with reading disabilities, and non-native users and it lowers the cognitive load.

Research shows that people who consider themselves skilled/good/high level readers read significantly faster when the text is well formatted.

Text: understanding

Co-funded by
the European Union

Combine text with images

- To increase understandability, add images that helps the user understand the content.
- Images can for example be used to:
 - Help the user focus on the most important parts
 - Add context
 - Describe steps in a process
 - Explain difficult or unusual words

Example: Combine text with images

The phases of a process, such as the project management life cycle, can be easier to understand when presented with both graphics and text.

Write understandable links

- All users benefit from understandable links. Users with assistive technology need to understand them also out of context, which is the way they are presented to them.
- Avoid links like "Click here" or "Read more"

Notes

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#link-purpose-in-context>

<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/#link-purpose-link-only>

Example: Understandable links

DO

- The links begin with a keyword
- The destination of each link is clearly stated in the link text
- Examples of clearly formulated links:
 - [Subscribe to our newsletter](#)
 - [Our privacy policy \(opens in a new window\)](#)
 - [Project Instruction \(pdf, 278kB\)](#)

Images and illustrations

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Images

For meaningful images:

- Describe in an alternative text (ALT) the information that the image carries
- Be short, focus on the relevant things

For decorative images:

- Mark them as decorative (do not skip)

Example

- Why did you choose the image?
- What do you want to convey to the readers?

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Do not rely on colour alone

- Colours are useful to convey meaning, but not all users see them the same way.
- For all users to get the same level of information, add something more than colour when you would like to highlight for example a link (e.g. bold, italics, underline ...)
- In diagrams, make sure data is distinguishable also in grey scale.

Example: Do not rely on colour alone

- Use at least one more way to convey information, in addition to colour.
- Links can be underlined or supplemented with an icon, for example.

Digital Dialogue: The Online Exchange

The internet has transformed how we communicate. Dive into the world of [online forums](#) where discussions span topics from science to pop culture. Engage in meaningful conversations that transcend geographical boundaries.

Nonverbal Communication: Beyond Words

Sometimes, the unspoken says the most. Delve into the art of [nonverbal communication](#) and learn how gestures, facial expressions, and body language convey emotions and intentions.

DON'T

Example: Do not rely on colour alone

- In a diagram, using colour alone can be difficult.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

DON'T

Example: Do not rely on colour alone

- Try the same colour in grey scale and you can see how difficult it is to distinguish between them.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

DO ✓

Example: Do not rely on colour alone

- Add something to the diagram to separate the bars from each other.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Audio / video

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Captions

- Captions can be manual or automatic
- Autocaptions are improving, but in many languages are still not good enough
- Use closed captions (CC), as open captions may disturb some users
- Presentations, video, online meetings, events
- ...

Exercise / activity

- Search for websites with “Read more” or “Click here” in your own language. If you find links with these terms, come up with more accessible link texts.
- Go to your national statistics authority and see how they handle diagrams. How could they have been made more accessible?
- Select “auto captions” in English in ppt, start speaking and see how the way you speak (distance to microphone, speed, whole sentences or broken up etc) impacts the quality of the captions.

Media and formats

Co-funded by
the European Union

Documents

Co-funded by
the European Union

PDF

- Apply the rules for texts and images mentioned earlier
- PDF documents need to be marked up so that screen readers can identify items such as headings and images
- Check if PDF is tagged in File Properties
- Add tags by selecting View > Tools > Accessibility > "Add Tags To Document."
- Remember: Make sure PDFs are not scanned images

Example: PDF document

The tags are established in a hierarchical structure, forming what is known as a "tag tree".

Social media

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Social media

- Use plain language/common words (there is little room for explanation)
- Use alternative text or even better; write out your text-in-image into the message
- Caption videos
- #CapitaliseEachWord in hashtags
- Use emojis sparingly

Exercise / activity

- Write a social media message in your favourite channel and make it as accessible as possible, using the five rules mentioned above.

adore
Accessibility in Digital Communication
Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

Resources

- [Microsoft Office built-in features](#)
- [Adobe built-in features](#)
- [Social media](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

Adore

Accessibility in Digital Communication Higher Education Curricula

Co-funded by
the European Union

[Publication license: CC-BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)
(Attribution and Share Alike)

Co-funded by the Erasmus + Programme of the European Union

The European Commission's support to produce this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Module B, content:

6. Accessible communication (recap)
7. What is accessible communication
8. Requirements in practice
9. Inclusive communication
10. Communication strategy
11. Accessible content
12. Accessible events - this document

Co-funded by
the European Union

12 Accessible events

Co-funded by
the European Union

PowerPoint

- PPT is made for presentation
- Users of AT often prefer alternative formats if you send the presentation to them.
- Combine text and images
- Do not clutter the slides
- Use large fonts

Preparing the room

- Furniture and placement
- Lighting
- Acoustics

Accessibility: visual

- Read out content or describe images
- Ask everyone to introduce themselves
- Include links to content
- Share documentation

Accessibility: audio

- Turn off microphone when not speaking
- Consider an external mic
- Use captioning
- Speak clearly and one at the time
- Share material

Exercise

- Set up meetings in Teams, Zoom, Google Meet, WebEx or similar online meeting system. Look at the accessibility features - how do they vary? Which system does (currently) provide more accessibility features?

Resources

- [Planning onsite events](#)
- [Accessibility features in Zoom](#)
- [Accessibility features in Teams](#)
- [Accessibility Features in Google Meet](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union